

JCMST

NOVI SAD

2023

Supported by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science, Technological development and Innovation of the republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT BOOK

11 – 13 October 2023

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

61(048.3)

THE PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology (2 ; 2023 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / The 2nd PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology 2023, 11-13 October 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor-in-chief Rajko Jović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Medicine, 2023. - 1 USB fleš memorija

Tiraž 150.

ISBN 978-86-7197-742-5

а) Медицинске науке -- Нове технологије -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 126492937

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

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ANALYSES OF BINARY AND TERNARY MICELLAR SYSTEMS OF HEXADECYLTRIMETHYLAMMONIUM BROMIDE, DODECYLTRIMETHYLAMMONIUM BROMIDE AND SODIUM DEOXYCHOLATE

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Introduction: When creating pharmaceutical drug formulations, the active ingredient's poor solubility can occasionally cause issues. In terms of solubilization properties, binary or multicomponent surfactant mixtures can have improved characteristics and a greater capacity for solubilisation than monocomponent surfactant solutions. The aim of this research is to formulate stable binary and ternary surfactant mixtures that can be used to solubilize active components, so the micellization of a binary and ternary mixture of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide and sodium deoxycholate has been investigated.

Materials and methods: Stock solutions of examined surfactants prepared in deionised water were mixed in binary and ternary systems in different molar ratios and their critical micellar concentrations were measured on temperatures (278.15-313.15K, in intervals of 5K) spectrofluorimetrically on Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Agilent, Germany) using pyrene as the probe molecule. Physico-chemical parameters of examined surfactant mixtures were calculated using Matlab

Results: In ternary micelles of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide, dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide, sodium deoxycholate the composition is dominated by hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide and deoxycholic acid anion. However, with the rise of the molar fraction of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide, it predominates. In binary micelles, both quaternary ammonium salts interact synergistically with one another and with the bile acid anion. i.e. have negative interaction coefficients. The absolute values of the coefficient of interaction between quaternary ammonium salts and bile acid are significantly larger than between them, so both quaternary ammonium salts in binary micelles interact more strongly with bile acid than with each other.

Conclusions: On each examined composition of the ternary mixture of surfactants the molar excess Gibbs energy of micelle formation is negative, which means that the real ternary mixed micelles is thermodynamically more stable than hypothetical ideal mixed micelles.

Keywords: drug formulations, mixed micelles, solubilisation, surfactants